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Part 1

Introduction

1 description

This document contains the consolidated results of the benchmarks used throughout the project. We compared the initial performance of LABS and WALBERLA with the resulting performance from the project as of November 2023.

There results are based on the benchmarks defined on D2.1 and extended with larger grids in D2.2 and D2.3. The benchmark files are stored in the IT4I forge <https://code.it4i.cz/eurohpc-scalable/showcases> and tagged. benchmarks_2.8 and benchmarks_3.1 correspond to the large grid use cases used with the respective version of LABS . benchmarks_2.8_small and benchmarks_3.1_small correspond to the small grid use cases used below 10k cores.

Part 2

Performance, accuracy and efficiency assessment

2 Scalability and Performance Evaluation

This section provides an updated view of the performance of the codes after the developments of the project. As mentioned on the previous deliverable, we have opted to use MLups to represent the performance. For the CPU benchmarks both the Karolina and the LUMI C systems were used. For GPU results were compiled on JUWELS BOOSTER and Karolina.

Overall, performance of the LABS code has been extensively improved on all metrics and performance bottlenecks have been lifted. For WALBERLA performance remains excellent and focus concerned the extension to additional models.

2.0.1 Lagoon case using Labs

This section highlights the performance of the lagoon use case. For v2.8 we used Karolina (AMD 7H12 cores) and for v3.1 we use LUMI C (AMD EPYC 7763). This was necessary as a performance issue was observed when rerunning the tests cases with v3.1 with a critical performance bottleneck at 4k cores. As evidenced here, this issue is not seen on LUMI C which suggests it's an execution environment problem that given the time frame we could not resolve alone¹.

Figure 1 shows a 30% improvement in MLups at 1024 cores up to 60% at 10240 cores and v3.1 is now able to run efficiently up to 20480 cores. Of this 30% improvement, 10% can be attributed to the change in architecture from Karolina to LUMI-C. Overall the improvement throughout all cases between v2.8 and 3.1 is from 15% to 25%. Please note the linear scale is based on v2.8 values and this is the case for all plots bellow as well. Scalability is much better and as will be seen in section 2.1 the improved memory requirements allowed for the execution of the use case without undersubscribing the nodes.

Figure 1: Lagoon performance on LABS (MLups)

¹it seems a change on UCX can explain some of the behavior we observed but as of December 2023 the issue remains.

2.0.2 S2A case using LABS/ProLB

For the S2A use case, some minor issues were observed and it was not possible to run the case on v3.1 on more than 2048 cores. This issue is under investigation by CS, nevertheless the performance gains are observed again here.

Figure 2: S2A performance on LABS/ProLB (MLups)

2.0.3 TurbulentChannel case using LABS/ProLB

For the TurbulentChannel case performance is excellent for v3.1. The memory improvements in the code allowed to run the case on 1024 cores with v3.1 whereas this was impossible with v2.8. Scalability is extended up to 20480 Cores with 80% efficiency compared to the linear scaling.

Figure 3: TurbulentChannel performance on LABS/ProLB (MLups)

2.0.4 COVO case using LABS/ProLB

The COVO test case highlight also the excellent improvement of performance (30% at 1024 cores to 50% at 10280 cores). The use case is able to run on a larger core count but performance is not so good at 20480. This can be explained by the fact that the use case is rather small for this number of cores and the ratio of computation versus communication becomes skewed.

Figure 4: COVO performance on LABS/PROLB (MLups)

2.0.5 Lagoon case using LABS/ProLB

Lagoon is one of our semi-industrial use cases along with S2A. For this complex case with advanced models and multiple refinement levels (see D2.1) performance improvements are again substantial and the scalability limit has been extended to above 20k. Also, this case would not run without undersubscribing the nodes above 4k cores to use one over two cores to improve memory per core so the MLUPs/CPU cost improvement is even more impressive than this curve suggests. The measurements of memory usage are in the section that follows.

Figure 5: Lagoon performance on LABS/PROLB (MLups)

2.1 Memory usage of Labs

Tables 1 and 2 showcase the memory use for lagoon and turbulent channel depending on the version. A detailed value is provided for the solver phase and a min/max view of all other phases for ease of reading. As can be observed between 2.8 and 3.1 a 50% improvement in memory consumption is observed for the solver. For the other phases a more limited but nevertheless improvements is also observed guaranteeing a lower memory requirements.

Table 1: Memory usage of LABS/PROLB - Lagoon case

Core number	2.8		3.1	
	Solver	Other steps (min - max)	Solver	Other steps (min - max)
1024	1864	550-1809	1050	586-1247
4096	875	289-1176	427	595-854
10240	818	298-942	526	643-833
20480			364	642-827

Table 2: Memory usage of LABS/PROLB - Turbulent Channel case

Core number	2.8		3.1	
	Solver	Other steps (min - max)	Solver	Other steps (min - max)
1024			1731	550-1611
2048	1987	510-1827	1025	553-1185
4096	1307	512-1603	651	559-937
10240	1027	437-1300	434	577-791
20480			359	606-768

This section shows the performance of WALBERLA on CPU and GPU. On the CPU version, the main improvements in the scope of the SCALABLE project were done in the mesh refinement algorithm. Details on these improvements are shown in deliverable 4.3. Thus, the following results are gathered using the same number of refinement levels as LABS and using the same resolution for the objects in the wind tunnel. This differs from deliverable 2.3 where all simulations done in WALBERLA used a uniform mesh. Furthermore, in an extreme scale version of the LAGOON is presented using almost 120 billion lattice cells. This showcases the capability of WALBERLA to handle such complex cases massively parallel.

As a next step, the developments on the GPU capabilities of WALBERLA are shown. During the SCALABLE project, it was possible to extend the capabilities of WALBERLA to handle refined cases also on the GPU. First results of this work are shown in this deliverable.

2.2 waLBerla performances and scalability

The LAGOON usecase results are presented with WALBERLA here. This test case consists of 561 415 WALBERLA blocks distributed to the MPI Ranks. The blocks reside on 10 levels of refinement, and the resolution around the landing gear is 0.000 25 m. Each block contains a uniform mesh of 8^3 cells, resulting in about 287 070 208 cells in total. In terms of cell counts, the setup is similar to deliverable 2.3. However, using mesh refinement leads to a more complex timestepping algorithm, including interpolations between the mesh levels. Furthermore, due to the block structured grid an overhead is introduced due to the data exchanges between blocks on the same process. This setup performs as expected very well up to 65k core on LUMI C. On 65 536 MPI Ranks each rank only holds about 4380 lattice cells which results in about 650 KB of memory used by each rank. This means that in this high core count, the entire problem can easily fit in the level three cache of the AMD EPYC 7763 processor. Furthermore, at higher scales less and fewer blocks reside on a single process, which significantly lowers the data exchanges within a single process. Those two effects lead to a certain amount of hyperscalability.

Figure 6: Lagoon performance on WALBERLA (MLups)

As a second benchmark, the LAGOON case was scaled up to around 120 billion cells. This was done by decreasing the resolution around the landing gear to $3.5 \cdot 10^{-5}$ m. The resulting problem is realized with 443 936 WALBERLA blocks that are distributed to the MPI Ranks respectively. The blocks reside on 8 levels of refinement, and each block contains a uniform mesh of 64^3 cells. As shown in, fig. 7 the test case runs with about two times the performance per core as the previous case. This is mostly explainable with the bigger block size and bigger mesh in general. The obtained results show very well the capability of WALBERLA to handle extreme scale scenario to almost unlimited sizes. This is not only the case in uniform scenarios but also in highly refined cases as shown here. The problem analyzed here would result in about $35 \cdot 10^{15}$ cells if executed on a uniform mesh. The benchmark was performed on up to 262 144 CPU cores on the HAWK supercomputer. The HAWK system was chosen because the CPU partition is much bigger than LUMI-C where we could only launch jobs on up to 65 536 cores.

Figure 7: Lagoon scaled to 120 Billion cells performance on WALBERLA (MLups)

2.2.1 S2A case using walBerla on CPU

For the S2A case, a similar setup as for LABS is used. Thus, the car is resolved with 0.0015 m resulting in 375 975 936 cells in total. This test case consists of 734 328 WALBERLA blocks distributed to the MPI Ranks and the blocks reside on 9 levels of refinement. Each block contains a uniform mesh of 8^3 cells. This setup performs as expected very well up to 65k core on LUMI C. Similarly to the Lagoon case in section 2.2 it is possible to fit all data in the level three cache on 65k cores. The hyperscaling in the benchmark can be explained similarly to section 2.2.

Figure 8: S2A performance on WALBERLA (MLups)

2.2.2 TurbulentChannel case using walBerla on CPU

For the turbulent channel test case, first a strong scaling benchmark is shown. The strong scaling is set up similar to the benchmark from section 2.0.3. Thus, a $896 \times 896 \times 896$ cells domain is set up. For WALBERLA

the uniform grid is distributed by using blocks of size 16^3 which results in about 175 616 total blocks. The results of the benchmark run are shown in fig. 9.

Figure 9: Turbulent Channel Strong scaling performance on WALBERLA (MLups)

Finally, a weak scaling run is performed with a uniform mesh of 16^3 on each processor. As the problem size increases more communication overhead is observed resulting a weak scalability of about 65 /

Figure 10: Turbulent Channel Weak scaling performance on WALBERLA (MLups)

2.2.3 Turbulent channel use case walBerla Weak scaling on JUWELS Booster

In this section, the performance of the TurbulentChannel test case on NVIDIA A100 GPUs is being evaluated. This has been done on the JUWELS Booster (JSC).

As a first benchmark, we show the TurbulentChannel in a weak scaling scenario. Due to the high parallel performance of GPU architectures, a large chunk size on each GPU is used. In this case, each GPU occupies a domain of 384^3 cells. In this benchmark, the performance of three scenarios is evaluated. In the first scenario, only double precision arrays and computations are used (DP). The second employs single precision for the

PDF array, transfers it to double precision in each compute kernel, performs all computations in double precision and finally stores the array back in single precision. The last scenario employs only single precision units for the computations and the storage. As shown in fig. 12 all scenarios show very good scaling results on up to 1024 GPUs. However, both the mixed precision case and the single precision case show higher overall performance. An analysis in terms of numerical errors caused in the different setups will follow in ??

Figure 11: Turbulent Channel Weak scaling performance on WALBERLA (MLups) on the Jewels Booster supercomputer

2.2.4 waLBerla strong scaling JUWELS Booster

Following the analysis from the weak scaling benchmark, we investigate the strong scaling behavior of the Turbulent channel using a domain size of 896^3 and scale it up to 1024 GPUs. As shown in devliverable 2.3 this domain size is rather small for a scaling experiment on up to 1024 GPUs. Nevertheless, it was possible to showcase a strong scaling efficiency of about 68 % for the DP case, and about 60 % for the mixed precision case. The 1.2 million MLUPs achieved with the mixed precision implementation lead to 1680 timesteps per second. It is important to note here that the performance advantage between the pure double precision and the mixed precision implementation are not as big anymore as in the weak scaling scenario. Clearly, this shows that more time is spent in the communication. Thus, the faster compute kernel does not pay off so much anymore. Similar, this is shown in an overall performance degeneration between the two cases. Still, the sheer number of timesteps per second can play a pivoting role in cases where a high number of timesteps is needed for convergence, as it is often the case in highly turbulence CFD analysis.

Figure 12: Turbulent Channel Strong scaling performance on WALBERLA (MLups) on the Juwels Booster supercomputer

3 Energy efficiency evaluation

Energy efficiency is expressed as a fraction of performance delivered by the hardware per single Watt consumed. In the area of the LBM codes, we express the performance in lattice updates per second.

3.1 walBerla on GPU

Since most WALBERLA optimisations focused on GPU-accelerated code, we have continued the energy efficiency of the WALBERLA cuda code. In addition to the results obtained in the previous deliverable D2.3, we have performed static GPU frequency tuning when strongly scaling the application. We evaluated the Lagoon usecase again, and this time also the CROR usecase. We wanted to see whether the optimal GPU configuration for the Lagoon will also fit the CROR, and how the optimum configuration will change when scaling and pushing the problem closer to the end of the scalability.

The analysis was performed at IT4Innovations' EuroHPC system Karolina. We could perform the scalability test on this system because the GPU direct issue we reported in D2.3 has been solved in the meantime. The system has 72 accelerated compute nodes, each consisting of 2 AMD EPYC 7763 (280 W TDP each) CPUs and 8 Nvidia A100-SXM4 (400 W TDP each) GPUs (576 GPUs in total). We have tuned the frequency of the GPUs' streaming multiprocessors (SM) only because scaling CPU frequency does not bring energy savings as we have shown in D2.3. The maximum turbo frequency of A100-SXM4 is 1410 MHz, nominal frequency is 1095 MHz.

Energy/power consumption reported is the summary of AMD RAPL and Nvidia NVML energy performance counters. The application has not been instrumented, so the average power is evaluated from the whole application execution.

3.1.1 walBerla GPU – Lagoon with uniform mesh

In this case, we see very good strong scaling up to 8 nodes, starting with 16 nodes scaling gets worse (16 nodes - 75% of linear, 64 nodes - 55% of linear). From the energy efficiency point of view, the best MLUPS/Watt has been reached when using two nodes (using one node was not possible due to memory limitation) – 12.45 MLUPS/W in the default, and 16.01 MLUPS in the optimal frequency configuration. The efficiency drops slightly if linearly scaling. However, when scalability worsens, the GPU SM frequency tuning cannot sanitize the efficiency drop, which goes below the single node efficiency when using the default settings. This is shown in Table 3 for results obtained on 16 and more compute nodes.

The optimal SM frequency configuration is 1095 MHz, which is the same found in deliverable D2.3 and this does not seem to change no matter the amount of GPUs used. In this configuration, the runtime extends less

than 2.9% but leads to energy savings between 13.77% and 22.43% as shown in Table 3. We expect that the optimum can change if the scalability gets worse, which is something a user should of course avoid. The impact of various SM frequencies on solver runtime is presented in Figure 14 and on energy consumption in Figure 15.

Figure 13: Lagoon strong scaling performance on WALBERLA (MLUPs) using uniform mesh on the Karolina supercomputer.

#nodes	#GPUs	SM freq [MHz]	solver runtime	energy consumption	MLUPs/W
2	16	default	201.47 s	757 kJ	12.45
		1095	+1.80 %	-22.43 %	16.01
4	32	default	103.16 s	773 kJ	12.31
		1095	-0.08 %	-20.37 %	15.23
8	64	default	58.40 s	857 kJ	11.29
		1095	+1.04 %	-18.24 %	13.94
16	128	default	33.15 s	998 kJ	10.03
		1095	+2.82 %	-14.64 %	11.60
32	256	default	24.07 s	1 454 kJ	7.03
		1095	+2.87 %	-15.94 %	8.31
64	512	default	11.41 s	1 969 kJ	5.84
		1095	+2.02 %	-13.77 %	6.78

Table 3: Optimal SM frequencies for the energy consumption reduction with a small impact on the run time (Lagoon with uniform mesh)

Figure 14: Lagoon (uniform mesh) executed on Karolina supercomputer – Impact of the SM frequency tuning on the run time

Figure 15: Lagoon (uniform mesh) executed on Karolina supercomputer – Impact of the SM frequency tuning on the energy consumption

3.1.2 waLBerla GPU – CROR

The CROR usecase uses an uniform mesh as well and performs well up to 128 GPUs. CROR achieves superlinear strong scaling with 2 nodes (16 GPUs) going slightly above the expected speedup ($2.09 > 2$). With 4, 8, 16 nodes the scaling degrades and goes below 70 % of the linear scaling. Similarly to Lagoon, one SM frequency worked the best for all the configurations. In this case, we have identified the optimal configuration as 1305 MHz (Table 4). It prolongs the computation runtime by 1.25 % in the worst case and can save up to 12.65 % of energy.

Figure 16: Strong scaling of CROR with uniform mesh (MLUPs)

#nodes	SM freq [MHz]	solver runtime	energy consumption	MLUPs/W
1	default	470.10 s	780 kJ	5.24
	1305	+0.43 %	-12.65 %	5.99
2	default	225.20 s	767 kJ	5.35
	1305	+1.25 %	-11.19 %	6.02
4	default	169.85 s	968 kJ	4.23
	1305	+1.21 %	-10.02 %	4.69
8	default	88.24 s	988 kJ	4.18
	1305	+1.08 %	-7.60 %	4.51
16	default	50.91 s	1 177 kJ	3.54
	1305	+0.35 %	-10.13 %	3.93

Table 4: Optimal SM frequencies for the energy consumption reduction with a small impact on the run time (CROR with uniform mesh)

This result is expected as CROR requires different algorithms than LAGOON (rotating methods for example). However, this means that depending on the scenario having a single SM frequency is not possible. On a positive note it is still possible to gain in energy efficiency on different scenarios.

Figure 17: CROR executed on Karolina supercomputer – Impact of the SM frequency tuning on the run time

Figure 18: CROR executed on Karolina supercomputer – Impact of the SM frequency tuning on the energy consumption

3.1.3 waLBerla GPU performance using mesh refinement

We have also performed the energy efficiency analysis of the Lagoon strong scaling while using mesh refinement. The strong scaling of Lagoon has a trend similar to the cases with a uniform mesh. With 2 and 4 nodes it is fair. On 8 nodes it is getting worse, i.e., 57% of linear scaling, which reports Table 5. The mesh refinement implementation in the WALBERLA is not yet completely finished (e.g., no communication hiding has been implemented yet), so we had to stop scaling the usecase when using 64 GPUs. The WALBERLA performs fewer lattice updates per second in comparison to uniform mesh usage, however to deliver the requested result, significantly less lattice updates are necessary. Due to that, the WALBERLA also reports virtual lattice updates, which is the estimated number of operations that would be performed if using uniform mesh. The results presented in Table 5 and Table 6 show decreasing MLUPs and MLUPs/W than the ones reached for uniform mesh cases, but the virtual MLUPs and virtual MLUPs/W are significantly higher – performance has increased 17.25x and energy efficiency 23.7x when comparing Lagoon with and without mesh refinement executed using 16 GPUs in the default frequency configuration.

While extending the runtime about less than 1.82% we reached energy savings of 6.13% up to 14.59%. The trends of runtime vs reduced GPU SM frequency in figure 19 and energy consumption in figure 20 are similar to what we saw with uniform meshes. The optimal SM frequency state-space search does not reveal a single optimal configuration as it was in the cases with a uniform mesh. Depending on a particular number of resources, frequencies 1305, 1245 and 1200 MHz work the best, while the frequency drops down hand by hand with the increased number of GPUs used.

#nodes	solver runtime [s]	solver speedup	MLUPs	virtual MLUPs
1	150.23	1.00	6 885.61	411 729.50
2	84.21	1.78	12 298.43	735 391.75
4	50.15	3.00	20 606.45	1 232 172.50
8	32.78	4.58	31 552.85	1 886 720.00

Table 5: Strong scaling of Lagoon with mesh refinement. One compute node has 8 GPUs.

#nodes	SM freq [MHz]	solver runtime	energy consumption	MLUPs/W	virtual MLUPs/W
1	default	150.23 s	193 kJ	5.63	336.58
	1305	+0.68 %	-6.99 %	6.15	367.83
2	default	84.21 s	231 kJ	4.88	291.75
	1245	+0.93 %	-14.59 %	5.76	344.51
4	default	50.15 s	261 kJ	4.36	260.99
	1245	+1.24 %	-6.13 %	4.64	277.53
8	default	32.78 s	354 kJ	3.29	196.80
	1200	1.82 %	-9.80 %	3.64	217.80

Table 6: Optimal SM frequencies for the energy consumption reduction with a small impact on the run time (Lagoon with mesh refinement)

Figure 19: Lagoon (with mesh refinement) - Impact of the SM frequency tuning on the run time

Figure 20: Lagoon (with mesh refinement) - Impact of the SM frequency tuning on the energy consumption

3.2 Labs

For LABS , we have continued our energy efficiency analysis of the CPU code presented in the deliverable D2.3, where we have reached 19.5% energy savings when executing Lagoon usecase. In LABS have been instrumented 80 regions for which we have identified an optimal configuration, however the iterative solver itself consisted of a single region. The limitation comes from the fact that the solver sub-regions are very short (in the range of milliseconds). Since the solver is supposed to take the majority of execution time in real-world usage, for the rest of the SCALABLE project, we focused on the dynamic tuning of such small regions executed iteratively.

Our approach used previously does not support such small regions, since for each evaluated hardware configuration we measure energy consumption, which has two consequences:

- Since we have energy consumption information for compute units (single CPU – Intel RAPL, HDEEM; while compute node – HDEEM), each region starts and stops with MPI and OpenMP barrier to synchronise processes and threads sharing the same CPU. Such barriers would have an extreme impact on solver performance.
- The power monitoring systems we usually use collect up to 1000 power samples per second, which means that for a region of 2 ms runtime, we may have one of two power samples, which we do not consider as reliable energy measurement to evaluate the impact of hardware configuration on power usage.

We extended the approach to support identifying and tuning iteratively executed fine-grain regions. For the whole loop (iterative solver), we identify the optimal configuration of parameters that will not be tuned inside the main loop. These should be parameters that require the barrier, e.g. CPU uncore frequency. This configuration is set, and later, the parameters that do not require a barrier (CPU core frequency) are tuned, while for the fine-grain regions, we measure runtime. We search for the configuration that does not impact the performance of these small regions while bringing maximum performance savings (the lowest CPU core frequency).

Additionally, the MERIC runtime system has been modified to support new features:

- MPI and OpenMP barriers are tuning domain specific – the barriers are inserted only if measuring energy, or according to the tuned hardware parameter (e.g CPU core frequency – on core barrier (in case of active hyper-threading), CPU uncore frequency – on socket barrier).
- Hardware parameters are set according to a tuning domain – CPU core frequency of a specific core is set by the process occupying the core. Previously, it was set by a single process on compute node because of barrier synchronising processes and threads on the compute node.
- Each process identifies a core it occupies.
- Processes and threads are bound to their CPU core, if not shared with another one, otherwise moved to another core where bound – MERIC at this moment does not allow to specify target affinity to set, this is space for future development.
- New light-weight MERIC regions that do not perform energy measurement.

3.2.1 Lagoon results

We have analysed the main solver loop of LABS 3.1 using the Lagoon usecase. The analysis was done on IT4Innovations' Barбора cluster, the same machine we used previously for LABS analysis reported in D2.3. The system consists of compute nodes with two Intel Xeon Cascade Lake 6240, that allow to tune CPU core frequency between the ranges 1.0–3.9 GHz (2.6 GHz is the nominal frequency, 3.3 GHz the peak turbo frequency when all cores are active) and uncore frequency 1.2–2.4 GHz. The usecase was executed using eight compute nodes.

The traditional MERIC region enveloped the solver loop, which specifies the configuration of the uncore frequency that remains unchanged during the solver execution. We have identified that the optimal uncore frequency is 2.1 GHz. The solver loop has been divided into four sub-regions, for which we have tuned the CPU core frequency only, where each process tunes the core it occupies. No additional synchronization is performed. Processes are synchronised by the MERIC at the end of the solver loop.

	CPU configuration	% of iteration runtime
solver loop	2.1 GHz uncore	100 %
region #1	2.5 GHz core	5 %
region #2	2.9 GHz core	13 %
region #3	2.6 GHz core	24 %
region #4	3.0 GHz core	58 %

Table 7: LABS main solver regions with its optimal CPU configuration for Lagoon usecase on Barbora super-computer.

	1 iteration runtime [s]	energy [J]	energy efficiency [MLUPS/W]
default	0.59	1437.15	0.051
static	0.60	1383.36	0.053
dynamic	0.60	1283.52	0.057

Table 8: LABS main solver energy efficiency analysis results for Lagoon usecase on Barbora supercomputer.

3.3 Summary

This document highlights the performance evaluation of WALBERLA and LABS derived from the optimisations of the SCALABLE project. During the project the scalability of LABS was extended up to 20k cores on CPU and a prototype GPU version was created. Overall raw performance was improved.

Additionally, we have performed an energy efficiency analysis of GPU WALBERLA when strongly scaling and dynamic analysis of the LABS main solver loop. For the fine-grain dynamic tuning it was necessary to come with a new approach how to tune sub-100ms regions, which was the limitation of our approach at the beginning of the project. Major modification of the MERIC runtime system was necessary to implement support fine-grain tuning. Using the dynamic tuning the energy efficiency of the Lagoon usecase has increased from 0.051 MLUPS/W to 0.057 MLUPS/W.

In case of the WALBERLA we have shown significant energy savings for all three evaluated usecases, moreover we showed how the approach works when scaling the application. Based on experiments with uniform mesh, it seems that it is enough to analyse the impact of the selected frequency spectrum on the smallest amount of resources (1 or 2 compute nodes in our cases) and use the found optimal frequency for larger scales. The lowest frequencies the GPU allows to be set should be avoided because these frequencies cause high performance penalties, leading to an increase in overall energy consumption. The approach to identify the optimal configuration should be step by step reduction of GPU SM frequency from the maximum turbo frequency down until the performance penalty exceeds a specified limit.

Despite the WALBERLA with mesh refinement implementation not yet fully completed, its performance, as well as energy efficiency, has been improved significantly in comparison to its uniform mesh usage. Performance has been improved 17.25x and energy efficiency 23.7x when comparing Lagoon with and without mesh refinement executed using 16 GPUs in the default frequency configuration. For the same reason, the optimal GPU configuration is not constant when strongly scaling. However, since the trends of frequency reduction on the performance and energy consumption have similar trends as in the case of uniform mesh, the approach to identify the optimal configuration can also be used in this case. Moreover, when increasing the number of provided GPUs, the starting point configuration should be the optimal configuration identified for a smaller number of GPUs used.

4 Labs POP analysis

For the POP analysis of the final LABS solver v3.1, Turbulent channel as an academic and Lagoon as a semi-industrial test cases were selected. The analysis were performed on both LUMI-C and Karolina GPU clusters to collect as much performance data as possible. The standard LUMI-C nodes with 128 cores and 256 GB of memory per node do not have enough memory to allow tracing of the small-scale runs with 1024 processes and less in case of Turbulent channel and with 512 processes and less in case of Lagoon test case. On the other hand, there are only 72 nodes in the Karolina GPU with 128 cores and 1024 GB of memory per node, which do not permit to execute the large-scale runs with 16384 processes and more. In addition, at the time of the measurements, the Karolina nodes did not provide the HW counters necessary to evaluate some of the performance metrics, e.g IPC or CPU frequency. This issue is being investigated by IT4I.

In order to be able to handle the size of the trace files, the data collection was limited by instrumentation to only 10 time steps of the solver, starting from the time step 50 in both test cases. Please note that in

deliverable D2.3, we have evaluated 20 time steps, meaning that the presented elapsed times must be doubled for a proper comparison.

The POP-based metrics were obtained using the BSC performance tools Extrae, Paraver, and Basic Analysis.

4.1 Analysis using Turbulent channel case

4.1.1 analysis on Karolina

We can observe very good strong scaling up to 8192 processes with the efficiency of 82% on Karolina cluster, see figure 21 and table 9. The moderate drop of the global efficiency at 2048 processes, visible in figure 22, repeated in multiple runs of the tracing job. Besides some algorithmic issue of the code, it might be caused also by some CPU noise or temporal frequency throttling of some nodes, since it affected both load balance and communication efficiencies.

Figure 21: LABS solver Turbulent channel strong scaling on Karolina.

Figure 22: LABS solver Turbulent channel efficiency metrics of 10 time steps on 8 - 64 nodes (128 processes per node) of Karolina.

Table 9: Overview of the Speedup, IPC and Frequency of LABS solver Turbulent channel 10 time steps on 8 - 64 nodes of Karolina.

Number of processes	256	512	1024	2048	4096	8192
Number of nodes	2	4	8	16	32	64
Elapsed time [s]	4.34	2.19	1.13	0.70	0.31	0.17
Speedup	1.00	1.98	3.85	6.15	13.96	26.15
Scaling Efficiency	1.00	0.99	0.96	0.77	0.87	0.82

4.1.2 analysis on LUMI C

The figure 23 shows that scaling starts to degrade at 16384 processes on LUMI and is limited by the increasing load imbalance, as indicated in 24. The two points above the ideal scaling are rather caused by a mild load balance issue also at the base 2048-processes run. Slightly lower average frequency can be also observed for that run in table 10. Please note that the similar degradation at the 2048 processes was observed also on Karolina cluster, see the subsection above. The load balance at this configuration will be investigated by CS.

Figure 23: LABS solver Turbulent channel strong scaling on LUMI.

	2048	4096	8192	16384	
Global efficiency	64.33	72.43	66.73	65.08	Percentage(%)
-- Parallel efficiency	64.33	83.19	77.15	68.70	
-- Load balance	66.83	90.94	90.13	71.32	
-- Communication efficiency	96.26	91.48	85.60	96.33	
-- Serialization efficiency	98.43	96.05	92.71	99.16	
-- Transfer efficiency	97.79	95.24	92.33	97.14	
-- Computation scalability	100.00	87.07	86.49	94.72	
-- IPC scalability	100.00	87.48	88.89	109.72	
-- Instruction scalability	100.00	98.05	95.22	90.08	
-- Frequency scalability	100.00	101.51	102.19	95.83	

Figure 24: LABS solver Turbulent channel efficiency metrics of 10 time steps on 8 - 64 nodes (128 processes per node) of LUMI.

Table 10: Overview of the Speedup, IPC and Frequency of LABS solver Turbulent channel 10 time steps on 16 - 64 nodes of LUMI.

Number of processess	2048	4096	8192	16384
Number of nodes	16	32	64	128
Elapsed time [s]	0.72	0.31	0.17	0.13
Speedup	1.00	2.34	4.32	5.52
Scaling Efficiency	1.00	1.17	1.08	0.69
Average IPC	1.30	1.14	1.16	1.43
Average frequency [GHz]	2.98	3.03	3.05	2.86

4.2 analysis using the Lagoon case

There are missing performance data for runs with 4096 processes due to an identified bug in the FluidMotion step, that will be fixed by CS.

4.2.1 analysis on Karolina

When comparing with execution times of the LABS v2.8 from deliverable D2.3, we can observe 1.7x speedup for 16 nodes and 1.8x speedup on 64 nodes, even on the runs that were affected by the tracing overhead. The scaling efficiency is still above 70% on 8192 processes, see figure 25 and table 11. Similarly as in the Turbulent channel case, the scaling is limited by increasing load imbalance, as shown in Figure 26.

Figure 25: LABS solver Lagoon strong scaling on Karolina.

	256	512	1024	2048	8192	
Global efficiency	83.57	84.53	74.40	72.17	66.90	
-- Parallel efficiency	83.57	82.03	83.05	79.52	74.72	
-- Load balance	86.22	86.27	85.20	81.73	78.54	
-- Communication efficiency	96.94	95.08	97.48	97.30	95.13	
-- Serialization efficiency	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	
-- Transfer efficiency	96.94	95.08	97.48	97.30	95.13	
-- Computation scalability	100.00	103.05	89.59	90.76	89.53	
-- IPC scalability	-	-	-	-	-	
-- Instruction scalability	-	-	-	-	-	
-- Frequency scalability	-	-	-	-	-	

Figure 26: LABS solver Lagoon efficiency metrics of 10 time steps on 8 - 64 nodes (128 processes per node) of Karolina.

Table 11: Overview of the Speedup, IPC and Frequency of LABS solver Lagoon 10 time steps on 8 - 64 nodes of Karolina.

Number of processes	256	512	1024	2048	8192
Number of nodes	2	4	8	16	64
Elapsed time [s]	1.23	0.63	0.35	0.18	0.05
Speedup	1.00	1.96	3.56	6.68	22.88
Scaling Efficiency	1.00	0.98	0.89	0.84	0.72

4.2.2 analysis on LUMI

Both the execution times and global efficiencies are very similar on LUMI and Karolina, yet there is one substantial difference. On Karolina the load balance degrades with scale as usual, but on LUMI, the load balance efficiency is improving with higher scale surprisingly, as shown in figure 28. The scaling is then ideal for the measured scale, see figure 27. Note that also IPC and average frequency is slightly increasing with scale, as reported in table 12. With such a trend, instruction scaling might be a potential limiting factor for higher scales.

Figure 27: LABS solver Lagoon strong scaling on LUMI.

Figure 28: LABS solver Lagoon efficiency metrics of 10 time steps on 8 - 64 nodes (128 processes per node) of LUMI.

Table 12: Overview of the Speedup, IPC and Frequency of LABS solver Lagoon 10 time steps on 8 - 64 nodes of LUMI.

Number of processes	1024	2048	8192
Number of nodes	8	16	64
Elapsed time [s]	0.39	0.18	0.05
Speedup	1.00	2.21	8.12
Scaling Efficiency	1.00	1.11	1.02
Average IPC	1.22	1.27	1.29
Average frequency [GHz]	2.36	2.36	2.38

4.3 Summary

We can conclude that the performance of the solver was significantly improved in both the execution time and the efficiency metrics, when comparing with the previous versions. E.g. communication was substantially improved, namely the transfer efficiency that was the limiting factor of the scaling. Currently it shows very good values above 95% most of the time.

One of the findings reported in deliverable D2.3 was that LABS v2.8 runs more efficiently with 64 processes per node than 128 processes per node due to decreased number of processes thus amount of communication while still sufficiently utilizing the memory bandwidth. The improved communication efficiency in LABS v3.1 reduces the high process count penalty and allows to utilize the computation power of the remaining cores of the node.

The future optimization effort of the LABS development should be focused on mitigating the load imbalance, according the POP model.

Part 3

Numerical precision and impact on performance

At the beginning of the project and since then, there have been many discussions regarding the impact of numerical precision and the performance of hardware. Just using simple or half precision operations can double or quadruple the performance of some floating point units, and this is specially true on GPU hardware and IA uses. In SCALABLE, we strove to harness this performance lever to see if further MLUPs could be extracted from the hardware.

Two research actions were undertaken. First, on WALBERLA mixed precision operation were implemented in ???. Secondly, we tried to use the debugging and assessing floating point precision and reproducibility tool Verificarlo on LABS (see section 5)

5 *verificarlo*

Verificarlo is debugging and floating point precision tool allowing to evaluate the sensitivity to numerical precision and reproductibility. Our main objective was to try to identify in WALBERLA and LABS sections where the simulation is sensitive to the numerical precision and test reduced numerical precision for non-sensitive kernels. Increased numerical precision requires more computing resources and energy. On today's GPU for example, switch to simple or lower precisions can lead to substantial runtime improvements. Unfortunately after more than a year of experimentation we had to give up on using *verificarlo* on our codes. Indeed, by default *verificarlo* requires to replace the compilation wrapper with its on and this creates problems on the target systems. Running this codes sequentially removing all MPI mentions proved unfeasable with the remained human resources. However, it was possible to experiment directly on the WALBERLA code using code generation. Results on WALBERLA inspired similar tests on LABS that will be carried out in 2024.

6 Conclusion

This deliverable contains the latest performance measurements and analysis of the codes on CPU and GPU. Overall, the SCALABLE project allowed the software to evolve beyond their initial conditions and support a wider range of systems (for example added GPU support) but also better raw performance and scalability and this results were obtained on EuroHPC JU systems. Furthermore, energy saving strategies have been highlighted allowing up to 20% energy savings with limited or no runtime impact a timely optimisation given the current energy cost crunch.

And finally, mixed precision simulation strategies for LBM codes have been devised yielding important runtime and memory requirement savings.

These optimisations and strategies have been transmitted into the official releases of the codes foreshadowing important savings for all academic and industrial users of the code.

